

Music Concerts Brian Paul Kaess & Garret Kaess attended by Brian Paul Kaess

In the early 1980's or so, Brian Paul Kaess & his friend Bob Gillis attended a *Judas Priest* concert at the Chicago Amphitheatre in Chicago. Also playing along was *Axe* (who opened) & *Iron Maiden*, who had a tall puppet dancing on the stage to the delight of the crowd. It was basically Heavy Metal stuff, which was more up Bob's alley than mine. *Iron Maiden* played songs like 'The Number of the Beast,' while *Judas Priest's* set list included 'You've Got Another Thing Comin' & 'Livin after Midnight'. They even drove a motorcycle onto the stage, revving it up as the crowd roared! In 1990, Brian Paul Kaess went to see *Tina Turner* and *Richard Marx* (from suburban Chicago) play in the Neckarstadium in Stuttgart, Germany, with his aunts Arnhild Kaess-Lehmann and Ursula 'Uschi' Kaess. In June 9, 2000, he saw *the Cure* in concert (during their North American Dream Tour) with Mayte Urbina Pereda at the (now defunct) World Music Theatre in Tinley Park, Illinois. They played songs like Fascination Street and Just like Heaven, a form of 'Goth Rock.' The music blared and seemed less crisp than on the radio or album. We relaxed on the vast lawn as they played.

Garret Thomas Kaess & Chris Aguda saw *Guns N' Roses* in concert at Alpine Valley in southern Wisconsin in 1991 or so I believe, amidst the pouring rain, when they (Garret & Chris) were literally sliding down the side of a muddy hill, but still enjoying the music! Brian Paul Kaess saw *the Drovers*, an Irish band, in concert in Chicago during the 1990's with workpals Teri Yak, Marci and others, perhaps at *the Heartland Cafe* in Rogers Park. I remember obtaining their CD.

Moreover, I saw the *Chicago Symphony Orchestra* twice at Orchestra Hall (1995 & 2000) in Chicago, the last time being with my 2nd wife Mayte Urbina Pereda. I heard pieces like Aaron Copland's "Fanfare for the Common Man", and perhaps Mahler's Symphony No. 9, as well as composers like Wagner and Tschaikovsky; Daniel Barenboim was Musical Director and Sir Georg Solti may have conducted a couple of the pieces. Brian Paul Kaess also saw *Ensemble Español* (Spanish Dance) twice (once with Bonnie Aguda) in concert at Northeastern Illinois University (where Brian was an *alum*) in Chicago during the early 1990's. The *Ensemble* specialized in Flamenco and traditional Spanish Dance.